

RFID Based Parking Slot Allocation

Sherin Babu
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
sherinbabu@mca.ajce.in

Dr. Paulin Paul
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
paulinepaul@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract — A radio frequency identification (RFID)-based parking slot detection system's goal is to make it easier for vehicles to find vacant spaces in a parking lot and identify whether they are available. Finding a parking space at events has grown challenging due to the significant expansion in vehicle availability and usage in recent years. The objective of this study is to develop a mechanism for efficiently allocating available spaces in parking lots at event locations. The proposed system will be implemented in an event management system, mainly for government events. Drivers will not have to wait long for their vehicles to be identified because the tags will do it instantly. Only registered tags (users) are permitted to enter, which will also assure security. The proposed system has been implemented with the help of the ESP32 board.

Keywords— RFID tags, RFID reader, I2C LCD Display, ESP32, Buck Converter

I. INTRODUCTION

RFID is an automatic identification and data-gathering system that transmits information from the reader to the tagged module using radio frequency waves. RFID makes use of tags to identify objects. Every tag has a different tag- id. The two primary types of tags are passive tags and active tags. Compared to active tags, passive tags are more prevalent and less expensive. Passive tags have more memory and no battery. The two components of Radio Frequency Identification are tags and readers (RFID). The reader is an electrical device that uses one or more antennas to send radio waves while receiving signals from RFID tags.

Figure 1. Working of RFID

RFID transmits and receives data using electromagnetic waves in the radio frequency band. RFID tags are utilized in various sectors, from security access to product tags at retail stores.

The use of RFID in parking systems is intended to offer quick fixes for issues that arise in parking lots. This paper proposes an automatic RFID-based access control system for the parking space in event venues using ESP32 hardware and Arduino IDE software. The system is designed to distinguish between authorized and unauthorized attendees. The RFID reader reads the RFID tag attached to the user invitation and checks it for matching with unique stored identifications for granting access.

RFID tags, an RFID reader, an I2C LCD, and an ESP32 make up most of the system's parts. At the parking lot's entrance, the RFID reader enables the identification of RFID tags. It records the user ID and checks to see whether it matches any already recorded IDs. If the captured user ID matches any stored IDs, access is granted; otherwise, access is denied.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A car parking system was proposed by P. Dhanabalraj, L. Gopinath, K. Kumar [1]. This concept utilizes a fundamental sensor enabled function and a microcontroller Arduino. These infrared sensors can detect objects when they come within a set distance.

Akshay P M, Murugesh K, and Yashketan Patra [2] proposed an IoT-based system based on electromagnetic RFID tags. Using the vehicle number, we determine whether the vehicle has been reserved.

With the use of a technique developed by Mohan P. Thakre, Payal S. Borse, Nishant P. Matale, and Padmini Sharma [3], the RFID card may store a variety of user data, including the vehicle's number, the owner's name.

An RFID based parking system with a barrier was proposed by Amritayan Chatterjee, Somnath Manna, Md Azizur Rahaman [4]. If the car has no tag, the barrier will stay closed.

The main menu in the model developed by Horng-Lin Shieh, Wen-Sheng Chang, Shih-Fong Lin, and Syu-Bang Jhang [5] comprises three components: the control system, management system, and database system.

III. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

A. RFID Reader

The RC522 module has eight pins in total. The pins support various communication protocols and serve different purposes. The primary function of MF RC522 is providing contactless communication at 13.56 MHz. It contains a modulation and demodulation algorithm, which helps to provide communication at 13.56 MHz. The module uses SPI to communicate with microcontrollers.

Figure 2. RFID Reader

B. RFID tags

A radio frequency identification tag (RFID tag) uses electronic data when communicating with a reader module. Most RFID tags have at least two components. The integrated circuit (IC) involves specialized processes such as data storage, processing, modulation, and demodulating radio-frequency signals. The other component is the antenna, which is used to transmit and receive the signal.

The RFID card has unique physical characteristics and is used for specific applications. The RFID card is distinguished by its prominent physical characteristics and is used for specific applications. Every RFID card has an antenna attached to an RFID IC, allowing it to receive, store, and transmit data through radio waves. RFID cards typically, do not have an internal power source and use passive RFID technology—the RFID reader's electromagnetic energy collected and transmitted powers RFID card.

Figure 3. RFID Tag

C. ESP32

ESP32 is a feature-packed microcontroller unit. The main feature of this MCU is that it contains built Wi-Fi and Bluetooth connectivity. It can perform in both ways—one as a standalone system and the other as a secondary device. In the case of Arduino UNO, we need to connect the ESP32 module externally. In the case of ESP32, we do not have to connect it externally because it is already built in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth functionality is provided through its SPI / SDIO or I2C / UART interfaces.

The ESP32 is the ESP8266's successor. It was designed for industrial use. It is appropriate for various IoT applications due to its low cost, small size, and low power consumption. Bluetooth LE, Wi-Fi, Ethernet IP, and other industrial Ethernet protocols such as Modbus TCP are supported. ESP32 works with Arduino IDE.

Fig 4. ESP32

D. I2C LCD Display

The I2C 16x2 Arduino LCD Screen uses an I2C communication interface. It can show 162 characters on two lines with a blue backdrop and white characters. For showing text, numerals, and special characters, the character LCD is perfect. A small add-on circuit (backpack) is built into LCDs and is mounted to the LCD module's back. The module has an adjustable potentiometer for adjusting the intensity of the LED backlight, as well as a controller chip that handles I2C connections.

I2C LCDs have the benefit of simple cabling and require two data pins to drive the LCD. It has a total of 20 male pins. Out of the 20 pins, 16 pins are faced toward the rear side, and four pins are faced toward the front side. The 16 pins are used for connecting to a 16x2 LCD. The other four pins are SDA and SCL.

Figure 5. LCD Display

E. Buck Converter

Most modern power conversion in low-power DC/DC conversion applications involves three types of power converters: Buck, Boost, and Buck-Boost Converters. Buck converters are mainly used as point-of-load converters for PCs, laptops, and USBs on the go. The specified input voltage is stepped down to achieve the desired output using a buck converter. Buck converters convert the fixed dc input signal to a different, lower-value dc signal at the output. This indicates that it is built to have an output dc signal with a smaller magnitude than the applied input.

Figure 6. Buck Converter

IV. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system includes an LCD, an ESP32 Node MCU, an RFID reader, RFID tags, and an I2C module. The brain of the proposed system is the ESP32 Node MCU board. When the card is displayed, the card reader device reads the data. The suggested model's output will be displayed on the LCD. The LCD will display the remaining slot count and the allocated spot.

Figure 7. Circuit Diagram

The system Implementation is broadly classified into:

1. Authentication

An RFID reader can tell who is authorized and who is not when a guest arrives at the venue. The RFID reader examines the RFID tag attached to the user invitation and verifies that it matches the unique identifications stored before allowing access.

2. Slot allocation

When the guest's identity has been confirmed, a parking space is assigned from among the available spaces. Afterward, when another visitor arrives, they are given

slots from the remaining open ones, omitting the occupied ones. There are a total of eight slots available. A random slot is assigned to the user from among the available spaces. When another user arrives, another random slot is assigned.

3. Displaying the balance Slots

In the system the LCD screen which is a component of the system displays the allotted slot and the remaining available slots.

V. RESULTS

The suggested system uses a prototype model that includes fundamental parts such as an RFID reader, an RFID tag and an ESP32 microcontroller board. Three steps make up the majority of the essential work. The reader first scans the tag to see if the stored ID matches the one on the tag. If a match exists, only the second phase—the slot allocation—can take place. An LCD displays the assigned slot. The allotted slot is subtracted from the total number of slots in the following phase to determine the balance of slots.

Figure 8. Initial Diagram

Figure 9. Slot Allocation

Figure 10. Balance Slots

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed solution, an RFID-based smart parking system, helps visitors smartly manage their parking to save time. As the visitor arrives, the card reader gadget reads the data from the card. The result of the proposed model will be shown on the LCD. The allotted slot and the number of remaining slots will be shown on the LCD. The suggested system will be implemented in a website for managing events, especially those held by the government. An RFID reader can tell who is authorized and who is not when a guest arrives at the venue. The RFID reader examines the RFID tag attached to the user invitation and verifies that it matches the unique identifications stored before allowing access.

TABLE.1 COMPARISON TABLE

Reference Number	Year	Working	Components
1	2021	sensor enabled function	Arduino microcontroller IR Sensors
2	2019	Dijkstra’s Algorithm to find the shortest path between car and the parking slot.	Arduino microcontroller RFID Tag
3	2021	IR sensor detects the vehicle	ESP12 Node MCU IR Sensor
4	2019	Barrier gate is used	EM18 RFID reader module
5	2013	an access control system for parking	RFID module RC522 NodeMCU V3 hardware

After comparing, we found that RFID-based parking can be implemented in various ways. The results are RFID RC522 reader is better than the EMI8 reader. The main differences between EM-18 and RC522 RFID Modules are that EM-18 is based on 125 kHz Radio Frequency Communication while RC522 is based on 13.56 MHz Frequency. Most Arduino boards lack independent Wi-Fi or Bluetooth capabilities They demand that an additional Ethernet shield be used. TheEsp32, on the other hand, comes equipped with Wi-Fi. TheEsp32 is now better suited for IoT projects. The proposed system consists of trending technologies and has various aspects that can be implemented in the future to enhance and improve the experience by providing real-time tracking of the vehicle.

VII. REFERENCES

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